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Palaw'an Language Preservation: Exploring Linguistic Practices in Local Communities

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the techniques employed by the Palaw'an people in preserving their language, as well as the challenges they faced to protect it. The data was gathered from a total of 396 respondents. Slovin's formula, frequency distribution, mean, and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient were the utilized statistical tools. Most respondents were in the age range of 23 to 32, predominantly female, and had attained an educational level up to Junior High School. The majority were identified as pure-blooded Palaw'an, and held no position in the community. Everyday conversations play a crucial role in preserving the Palaw'an language, however, challenges persist, particularly in the diminishing practice of native songs, sayings, and oral traditions. The challenges encountered in preserving the language of Palaw'an people did not show a significant relationship with their demographic attributes, such as age, sex, highest educational attainment, and ethnicity. However, a distinct correlation was observed, specifically regarding one's position within the group: as individuals move to higher positions, they appear to encounter fewer challenges, potentially due to increased resources, connections, or authority that enable them to address issues more effectively. This underscores their significant role in promoting language transmission and inspiring younger generations to preserve linguistic practices.

Keywords: *preservation, Palaw'an, language, challenges, techniques*

Introduction

The Philippines, renowned for its rich and diverse culture, stands as a testament to the historical influence of various colonizing nations. This cultural mosaic is vividly reflected in the multitude of languages spoken across the archipelago- up to 187, each with its unique history and origin. Despite enduring centuries of Spanish and American rule, many indigenous languages have persevered (Temelkova, 2022). However, the linguistic landscape in the Philippines faces a daunting challenge. According to the Living Tongues Institute for Endangered Languages, the country is among the top 10 "language hotspots" globally, with several languages nearing extinction (Mamon, 2021).

According to O'bery (2022), a language can die for several reasons. Some can be due to geopolitical conditions or even natural disasters. In the 21st century, the main reason for a language dying is that people simply abandon it in favor of another language. He added that preserving an endangered language should be considered as important as preserving an endangered wildlife species because language is so much more than a way to communicate- language is a large part of cultures. Language is the main medium through which a culture promotes and preserves its heritage. The world's languages have been used for centuries as a way to pass down some of the best stories of ancestors and other rich cultural histories. Most cultures still rely on local languages to communicate their histories, folklore, songs, and poems. An endangered language means its culture is also on the brink of collapse. Their survival is crucial in maintaining a diverse world. Many languages also represent the uniqueness their parent culture has. Preserving a language means preserving its very community and culture, which is essential to maintaining a diverse and inclusive world.

Villasin- Young (2022) stressed that protecting indigenous languages (ILs) means preserving cultural diversity. ILs are part of peoples' cultural heritage, which makes language crisis a cultural crisis. Everything is connected through language – including transfer of knowledge and cultural practices. Language experts believe that a language condition could also indicate the overall condition of Indigenous Peoples (IPs). Moreover, the protection of ILs hinges on the rights of IPs – among the country's vulnerable and marginalized groups. Further, IL preservation and revitalization could be fraught with challenges.

Alejan et al. (2021) posited in their study that losing one's language is inevitable. Several factors keep on challenging the existence of a language. Language choice of humans also affects the indigenous languages, and the failure to pass one's native language contributes to its loss. Everyone is responsible for its indigenous language. The choice to learn, use, and share with others is already preserving it. As long as the speaker lives, continues to use, and regenerate their heritage language to the younger speakers, the language lives.

In the context of a linguistic crisis, Palawan emerges as a particularly significant place for study. Known for its remarkable linguistic diversity, the island province is home to 52 distinct dialects, each reflecting the cultural richness of its communities. Among these languages, the Palaw'an language holds a central place, not only as a means of communication but also as a key element of cultural identity. Spoken by over 11% of the population (Omniglot, 2023), the Palaw'an language is an essential part of the province's heritage. However, like many indigenous languages worldwide, it faces the threat of extinction.

In response to these challenges, the Palaw'an community has been actively engaged in efforts to preserve their language. These preservation initiatives are vital to ensuring that future generations continue to speak and cherish the language as part of their cultural legacy.

This study aimed to examine the active preservation efforts of the Palaw'an community and the challenges they faced in their pursuit of linguistic survival. It addressed key research questions concerning the socio-demographic profile of the Palaw'an people, including factors such as age, sex, highest educational attainment, ethnicity (whether they were pure-blooded or half-blooded), and their position in the community. The study also explored how the Palaw'an people preserved and protected their language as part of their culture, the challenges they encountered in this process, and whether there was a significant relationship between their socio-demographic profile and the difficulties they faced in language preservation.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the socio-demographic characteristics of the Palaw'an community and the challenges they face in language preservation. The descriptive aspect focused on analyzing demographic factors such as age, gender, educational attainment, ethnicity (pure-blooded or half-blooded), and position in the community.

Additionally, it assessed the techniques Palaw'an people use to protect their language and the difficulties they encounter. The correlational component explored potential relationships between the demographic factors and the challenges identified. The study employed Slovin's formula with 95% level of confidence to determine a representative sample size of 396 respondents from the Palaw'an community. The choice of Slovin's formula was based on the need to achieve a statistically significant sample size while taking into account population variability and the margin of error.

A survey questionnaire was developed to gather the necessary data. To ensure the reliability and validity of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted with a smaller subset of the population, and necessary adjustments were made based on feedback. Frequency Distribution was employed to summarize the information gathered for the demographic profile of the respondents, the way they preserved and protected the existence of their language, and the challenges they encountered in preserving it. Mean was used to represent the average value of the variables within the demographic profile. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was employed to test the statistical hypothesis. It was utilized to identify if there was an association existed between the demographic profile of the Palaw'an people and the challenges they encountered in preserving their language. It provided insights into which factors, if any, played a significant role in the language preservation efforts. The study adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

	Brooke's Point	Bataraza	Frequency Quezon	Sofronio Española	Rizal	Total	% (n=396)
Age							
73 – 82	1	1	1	0	2	5	1.26
63 – 72	7	11	7	4	1	30	7.58
53 – 62	12	7	8	4	3	34	8.59
43 – 52	17	13	12	7	9	58	14.65
33 – 42	19	18	10	8	9	64	16.16
23 – 32	35	31	33	14	12	125	31.57
13 – 22	22	25	14	6	13	80	20.20
Sex							
Male	36	51	39	24	24	174	43.94
Female	77	55	46	19	25	222	56.06
Highest Educational Attainment							
None	25	15	15	7	6	68	17.17
Elementary Undergraduate	11	15	16	15	7	64	16.16
Elementary Graduate	20	13	10	6	6	55	13.89
Junior High School Level (Non-Completer)	22	28	15	8	16	89	22.47
Junior High School Completer	10	17	15	2	3	47	11.87
Senior High School Undergraduate	4	3	2	0	5	14	3.54
Senior High School Graduate	4	6	9	1	1	21	5.30
College Undergraduate	10	8	1	3	3	25	6.31
College Graduate	6	1	1	1	2	11	2.78
Vocational Graduate	1	0	1	0	0	2	0.51
Ethnicity							
Pure-blooded	103	97	80	42	45	367	92.68
Half-blooded	10	9	5	1	4	29	7.32
Position in the Community							
None	104	97	78	34	42	355	89.65
Barangay Captain	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00

Barangay Clerk	3	0	0	0	0	3	0.76
Barangay Health Worker	0	2	0	2	3	7	1.77
BNS	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.25
Chieftain	0	1	1	0	1	3	0.76
IPMR	1	0	0	1	1	3	0.76
Kagawad	0	2	0	0	1	3	0.76
Lupon	0	1	0	3	0	4	1.01
Pang Lima	1	0	2	2	0	5	1.26
Regional Chieftain	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.25
Secretary	0	0	1	1	0	2	0.51
Tanod	3	2	2	1	0	8	2.02
Tribal Treasurer	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.25

It can be seen from Table 1 that most respondents (31.57%) fell within the 23 to 32 age range, a critical period for active cultural participation and language transmission. Females comprised the majority (56.06%), reflecting their significant role in linguistic preservation, often as primary caregivers and educators within families. Educational attainment varied, with most respondents having attended Junior High School but not completing it (22.47%), and a substantial proportion (17.17%) having no formal education. This points out challenges in using reading and writing to preserve language, stressing the need for oral and practical learning approaches.

The majority (92.68%) are pure-blooded Palaw'an, reflecting the fact that language is naturally passed down through generations in families that share the same ethnic background. Most respondents (89.65%) did not hold formal positions within their communities, implying that language preservation relies heavily on informal social structures.

Table 2. Ways on How Palaw'an People Preserve and Protect the Existence of their Language as Part of their Culture

Indicator	Brooke's Point	Bataraza	Quezon	Sofronio Española	Rizal	Mean	Interpretation
I use this in my everyday conversations with my fellow tribespeople.	4.11	4.25	4.38	4.53	4.49	4.35	Highly preserved
I teach this to my younger tribespeople.	3.38	3.63	3.87	3.70	4.14	3.74	Highly preserved
I teach this to my acquaintances who speak a different language.	2.76	2.88	3.35	3.09	3.55	3.13	Moderately preserved
I read writings that are written/published in our language.	2.48	2.54	3.02	2.72	3.08	2.77	Moderately preserved
I listen to indigenous songs from our tribe.	2.65	2.64	3.14	3.44	3.12	3.00	Moderately preserved
I make a list of words so I don't forget them.	2.46	2.27	2.73	2.47	2.49	2.48	Fairly preserved
I use it in my social media interactions.	2.45	2.29	2.61	2.09	2.63	2.42	Fairly preserved
I use this in school and in my individual study.	2.15	2.42	2.53	2.44	2.86	2.48	Fairly preserved
I create songs, poems, essays, and other writings using it.	1.86	1.92	1.96	2.28	2.69	2.14	Fairly preserved
I encourage my fellow tribespeople not to forget it and to continue using it despite the prevalence of the major languages in the Philippines.	3.57	3.25	3.67	3.56	3.45	3.50	Moderately preserved
Weighted Mean	2.79	2.81	3.13	3.03	3.25	3.00	Moderately preserved

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Very Highly Preserved, 3.51–4.50 – Highly Preserved, 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Preserved, 1.51–2.50 – Fairly Preserved, 1.00–1.50 – Poorly Preserved

It can be gleaned from the table that majority of the respondents highly preserved their language through using it in their everyday conversations with their fellow tribespeople as evident on its mean, 4.35; and by teaching it to their younger tribe members with mean, 3.74.

Further, they moderately preserved it by encouraging their fellow tribespeople not to forget it and to continue using it despite the prevalence of the major languages in the Philippines as manifested by its mean, 3.50. The mean score of 3.00 signifies that the Palaw'an language was moderately preserved by the Palaw'an people. It validated the results of the study conducted by Montano (2021) revealing that individuals in Palawan upheld their indigenous language by actively using it in conversations among siblings and within their local communities. They maintained a consistent practice of employing their native language across different settings, including neighborhoods, workplaces, and interactions with respected figures beyond their immediate households, thereby ensuring its continuous use and preservation. Utilizing a language in everyday conversations is among the most prevalent yet highly effective methods of preserving it because according to Korneeva et al. (2019), language holds paramount importance as it serves as the primary vehicle for communication and the unity of people. It governs interpersonal and social interactions, coordinates practical activities, and contributes significantly to the shaping of ideological systems and national perspectives.

Moreover, language plays a vital role in storing information, organizing concepts, and molding human consciousness and self-awareness. Through language, individuals grasp their people's historical and present significance, connect with cultural heritage, and engage in the ongoing spiritual evolution of society and nation. It validated the Komisyon sa Wikang Filipino advocacy that children should be taught on the cultivation of local languages because the use of local languages not only in academic purposes but also in

daily interactions will reflect the Filipino identity of having a rich culture and languages as stated by Sunnexdesk (2021).

Table 3. *The Challenges Encountered by the Palaw'an People in Preserving Their Language*

Indicator	Brooke's Point	Bataraza	Quezon	Sofronio Española	Rizal	Mean	
I am not understood by my fellow tribesmen and other people.	2.92	3.24	3.32	3.12	3.45	3.21	Moderately encountered
I experienced mockery from other people.	3.41	3.52	3.35	3.16	3.27	3.34	Moderately encountered
None of my acquaintances wish to learn our language.	2.90	2.93	2.47	2.86	2.53	2.74	Moderately encountered
There are no longer any printed materials to read that are written in our language.	3.37	2.99	3.20	3.12	2.69	3.07	Moderately encountered
Our native songs, sayings, and other oral traditions are slowly disappearing, so the younger generation no longer knows them.	3.97	3.44	3.67	3.42	3.69	3.64	Often encountered
I don't have enough financial capability to create and reproduce dictionary of our language to share it with others.	3.68	3.35	3.52	3.72	3.43	3.54	Often encountered
No one is engaging with my posts on social media because they don't understand my stories.	3.28	3.35	3.13	3.28	3.04	3.22	Moderately encountered
I am not well understood by my teacher and fellow students in what I teach.	3.34	3.08	3.32	3.19	3.27	3.24	Moderately encountered
No one wants to read my stories because they are written in an uncommon language that they cannot understand.	3.35	3.08	3.06	2.84	3.08	3.08	Moderately encountered
My fellow tribespeople refuse my encouragement to use and teach our language to others.	2.63	2.64	2.64	2.44	2.71	2.61	Moderately encountered
Weighted Mean	3.29	3.16	3.17	3.11	3.12	3.17	

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Always Encountered, 3.51–4.50 – Often Encountered, 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Encountered, 1.51–2.50 – Seldom Encountered, 1.00–1.50 – Not Encountered

It can be seen that challenges such as; the slowly disappearing of the native songs, sayings, and other oral traditions that's why the younger generation no longer knows them, with mean, 3.64; and the lack of financial resources to create and reproduce dictionary of their language to share it with others, with mean, 3.54 are the often encountered problems of the respondents. Further, they moderately encountered mockery from other people as revealed by its mean, 3.27. The weighted mean 3.17 indicates that they moderately encountered challenges in preserving their language. The slow disappearance of the native songs, sayings, and other oral traditions is deeply concerning because according to Rogers (2020), language matters- spiritually, culturally, and emotionally.

When a language is lost, part of that culture is lost. By the same measure, when language is preserved, the traditions and customs continue living in the hearts and minds of those who understand it. Language is more than the sum of its parts: it's not just sentence structure and grammar, language is history and discourse, customs and heritage. Their struggle, specifically the financial constraints preventing the creation and reproduction of dictionary to share with others, coincides with the point raised by Chang-Castillo & Associates (2019) that one of the most common methods used to protect language was creating recorded and printed resources. According to them, recorded and printed documentation are essential for preserving languages' sound and context. The issue of experiencing mockery from others is a serious problem. According to Degawan (2019), because of years of discrimination, many indigenous parents choose to teach and talk to their children in the dominant languages- in order to create optimal conditions for their social success. Since their mother tongue is often used only by older people, an entire generation of indigenous children can no longer communicate with their grandparents. Recognizing these challenges holds vital importance for the Palaw'an people, enabling them to develop strategies to preserve their language effectively.

Table 4. *The Relationship Between the Socio-Demographic Profile of the Palaw'an People and the Challenges They Encountered in Preserving Their Language*

Demographic Profile	Critical Value	Tabulated Valued	Decision
Age	0.464	0.147	Accept Ho
Sex	1.000	0.000	Accept Ho
Highest Educational Attainment	0.035	0.462	Accept Ho
Ethnicity	-1.000	0.000	Accept Ho
Position in the tribe	-0.684*	0.015	Reject Ho
Religion	0.104	0.388	Accept Ho

* significant @ 5% level of significance

Testing the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age and the challenges they encountered in preserving their language, it can be seen in the table that its tabulated value (0.147) is lower than the critical value (0.464), therefore, the null hypothesis implying that there is no significant relationship between age and the challenges faced by the

Palaw'an people in preserving their language is accepted. This implies that the challenges they encountered in upholding their language were not influenced by age.

Further, the critical value (1.000) for sex is the maximum possible value for the Spearman rank correlation coefficient, suggesting a perfect correlation. The tabulated value (0.000) on the other hand indicates that there is no correlation between sex and the challenges encountered by the Palaw'an individuals in preserving their language, therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between sex and the challenges that the respondents' faced in preserving their language is accepted. This signifies that sex did not have an impact on the difficulties they faced in maintaining their language.

Moreover, the tabulated value (0.462) for highest educational attainment is higher than the critical value (0.035), it indicates that the computed Spearman rank correlation coefficient does not meet the threshold for statistical significance, therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the highest educational attainment and the challenges encountered in preserving the language of the Palaw'an people is accepted. This implies that the educational attainment had no influence on the challenges they faced in preserving their language.

Additionally, the critical value (-1.000) for ethnicity denotes a perfect negative correlation in Spearman's rank correlation, which is the strongest possible negative correlation. Its tabulated value of 0.000 indicates no correlation or a complete absence of a relationship between ethnicity and the challenges encountered in preserving the language of the indigenous population, therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between ethnicity and the challenges faced in preserving the language of the indigenous people is accepted. This means that ethnicity is not in any way connected with the challenges encountered by the Palaw'an community when it comes to preserving their language.

Since the critical value for position in the community is -0.684 and the tabulated value is 0.388, the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that there is a significant negative correlation between the position in the tribe and the challenges faced in preserving the Palaw'an language. This means that the higher the position of a specific Palaw'an individual, the fewer challenges he/she tends to face.

Conclusions

The Palaw'an people have successfully maintained their language across generations primarily by integrating it into their daily conversations and actively teaching it to younger members within the community. Nevertheless, certain obstacles persist. Traditional songs, sayings, and other forms of oral heritage are gradually fading, leaving many younger individuals unfamiliar with these cultural elements. Additionally, limited financial resources have hindered the creation and distribution of a community dictionary, which would otherwise help in preserving and promoting the language more broadly. Factors such as age, gender, education level, ethnicity, and religion have not significantly influenced these preservation challenges. Moreover, those in higher community positions encounter fewer difficulties in sustaining the language, indicating that leadership roles may positively affect preservation efforts. To address the challenges and enhance language preservation, it is recommended to develop culturally aligned educational resources, such as textbooks, dictionaries, and multimedia tools, with support from educational institutions and language preservation organizations. Additionally, community-based workshops and cultural events focused on traditional practices like storytelling, singing, and oral histories should be organized to reconnect the younger generation with their heritage. Utilizing digital platforms and social media to engage a wider audience, can further promote the Palaw'an language. Empowering local leaders through training and resource support will strengthen preservation efforts, while seeking funding from governmental and non-governmental organizations will provide essential resources. Finally, ongoing research and monitoring are crucial to assess the effectiveness of these initiatives and adapt strategies to the community's evolving needs. Through these collective efforts, the Palaw'an language can be safeguarded for future generations.

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